

IT TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

Rajabboyev Abdurahmat¹, Shodmonov Azizbek², Hiloliddin Abdusalomov³

^{1,2}Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, 2-course students,
English language and literature

³Scientific supervisor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6163473>

Annotation: In this article, we try to describe the importance of IT technology in education and facilities for everyone.

Key words: Communication technologies, TV, Radio, Online and mobile, hardware, software, tablets, teachers, students, 3D printing, social media networks, cloud computing.

The use of information and communication technologies in education can play a crucial role in providing new and innovative forms of support to teachers, students, and the learning process more broadly. Still, it's important to note that technology is a tool used in education and not an end in itself. The promise of educational technology lies in what educators do with it and how it is used to best support their needs.

Technology played and continues to play an essential role to deliver education to the students outside of school. Commendably, all countries were able to deploy remote learning technologies using a combination of TV, Radio, Online and Mobile Platforms. However, many children in low income countries did not participate in remote learning with about a third of low income countries reporting that 50% of children had not been reached in a joint UNESCO-UNICEF-World Bank survey. The pandemic has also led to significant losses in learning. School closures and limited access to remote learning means that Learning Poverty is likely to worsen from 53% to 63% especially in low-income countries if no remediation interventions are taken.

However, educational technology has its challenges, particularly when it comes to implementation and classrooms, according to Project Tomorrow. Additional concerns include excessive screen time, the effectiveness of teachers using the technology, and worries about technology equity. Teachers want to improve student performance, and technology can help them accomplish this aim. To mitigate the challenges, administrators should help teachers gain the competencies needed to enhance learning for students through technology. Additionally, technology in the classroom should make teachers' jobs easier without adding extra time to their day.

Technology provides students with easy-to-access information, accelerated learning, and fun opportunities to practice what they learn. It enables students to explore new subjects and deepen their understanding of difficult concepts,

particularly in STEM. Through the use of technology inside and outside the classroom, students can gain 21st-century technical skills necessary for future occupations.

Today, mobile technology can be used in numerous ways to enhance the classroom. On a basic level, it can be used to fulfill basic needs like making calculations, recording classroom lectures, and taking notes. However, this barely begins to scratch the surface of what mobile technology can do. This technology can be taken out during science field trips and used to document natural phenomena. Similarly, history field trips can be enhanced by taking photos of historically significant structures. Mobile technology is also important because it can allow students to collaborate using social networks in the classroom. Indeed, social networks are increasingly being valued for their ability to enhance the learning experience.

With increasing knowledge and technological progress of society; our country requires learning skills that could help it keep pace with the development of science and technology. Educational systems in a community and consequently education will not be able to separate from other social institutions, national and international interactions widely known in the global village. Education in the twenty-first century is the center from which all changes and developments arise. Information technology in education needs a culture. This culture needs to be learned along with the use of hardware resources. The system needs to be educated to use information technology; otherwise, purchase and transfer of technology and investment will be nothing but wasting resources. Although these technologies are not impartial in any sense they should be used as means for communicating information, in the existing social structures. However since the process of change and transformation is in the nature of human social institutions, the educational system is also prone to some alterations. But the fundamental problem is that what strategies should be adopted so that education systems in developing countries do not only follow developed countries but grow and progress base on their own needs in the path of progress. In this paper, after explanation about the role of information technology and its place in education in underdeveloped countries and Iran, a discussion is presented on how to enter the field of information society and how to use information technologies.

Technology plays an increasingly significant role in improving access to education for people living in impoverished areas and developing countries. Educational technology is not merely a matter of education and technology alone but is also about the societal culture wherein that educational technology is implemented.

Literatures:

1.en.m.wikipedia.org.

2.bscholarly.com

3.www.allisonacademy.com

4.https://educause.edu. books

5.https:soeonline.american.edu

6.https://citijournal.org

7.sciencedirect.com

8.educationcorner.com.

9.worldbank.org.